

Research and Development of Net-Centric Information Sharing Platform

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Abstract : Compared with traditional distributed environment, the net-centric environment brings on more demanding challenges for information sharing with the characteristics of ultra-large scale and strong distribution, dynamic, autonomy, heterogeneity, redundancy. This paper realizes an information sharing model and a series of core services, through which provides an open, flexible and scalable information sharing platform.

Keywords : net-centric environment, information sharing, metadata registry and catalog, cross-domain data access control

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